

Evaluating the Immunization Cold Chain of Pakistan: A Qualitative Case Study

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Abstract

The COVID-19 Pandemic has put a spotlight on the national immunization program of Pakistan. This paper is a qualitative study into the national immunization cold chain. We selected “Reliability” as our variable of interest. To measure this, we developed a questionnaire that addressed it through 3 main categories: delivery delays, quantity inadequacies, and unqualified products. Our findings are based on interviews with 16 individuals at various levels of the cold chain with an emphasis on the levels from districts to union councils. Thus, instilling a degree of validity to our results. Through these interviews we have built a narrative that aims to give a qualitative explanation to the question of the degree of reliability of the cold chain as well as the issues that its stakeholders face. Due to the breadth and richness of our interviews we have arranged and presented them under 5 themes: delivery delays; unqualified products; quantity inadequacies & procurement; end delivery; and managerial decisions comprising of budget, planning & human resource availability.

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

Immunization is a public health intervention that is important in alleviating a country's disease burden. A cold chain is a particular kind of supply chain that maintains a given temperature range (usually between 8 to 15 degrees Celsius), with regular and consistent storage and distribution activity (Gorar & Zulfikar, 2010). Immunization cold chain is a type of cold chain which focuses on the delivery of vaccines. It is therefore a set of rules and procedures that are designed to move the vaccines from the manufacturing point to the point where they are administered while keeping the vaccines under prescribed conditions. The diagram, taken from WHO's report on vaccine cold chains, depicts the vaccine cold chain by showing how vaccines move from one level to the other and the sort of data collected and analyzed at each level.

Image 1: Immunization cold chain network (WHO, 2021)

Statement of the problem

Vaccines have been heralded as one of the greatest feats in human health and development. They have the potential to save millions of lives by improving immunity against life-threatening diseases. They have helped us fight diseases such as influenza, tetanus, diphtheria, and measles, preventing around 2-3 million deaths each year.

Due to the significant health impacts of vaccines, immunization has become an indisputable human right and an important part of the primary health care. Immunization is critical not only for improving health of humans of all age but also to the prevention and control of disease outbreaks. It is a vital tool for global health security and fight against antimicrobial resistance.

Unfortunately, not everyone has equal access to vaccines. This leaves a huge chunk of human population including nearly 20 million newborns each year, at the risk of life-threatening diseases. Progress in terms of global vaccine coverage has been slow and in some countries it has even reversed. This is because, the vaccine cold chain underpins the performance of any immunization program. Failure to maintain the vaccine cold chain could result in lack of access to and reduced potency of the vaccines. Both of these results can significantly impact the global vaccine coverage outcomes. Third world countries like Pakistan that have limited resources available over a large population are at even higher risk. Pakistan's weak public health and immunization services are evident from the fact that it is one the two countries where polio remains an endemic. As a result, the performance of a vaccine cold chain is a high area of interest.

This study aims to explore and analyze the reliability of the immunization cold chain of Pakistan by incorporating the point of views of the relevant stakeholders.

Purpose

Over the last few decades, Pakistan has invested significantly on its immunization programs. Global organizations such as UNICEF and GAVI, the global alliance, have also contributed in their capacity to provide vaccines, trainings, and other services. Despite these efforts, the national vaccine coverage still remains below optimum level due to several bottlenecks in our vaccine supply chain.

This research tries to analyze the cold chain of Pakistan using the qualitative case study method. The purpose of the research is to improve understanding regarding the present condition of and the problems present in our vaccine cold chain ecosystem. By analyzing the issue using the stakeholders' point of views, the research aims to reach at the underlying causes of the problems and possibly identify practical solutions to those.

Research question

In order to analyze the cold chain of Pakistan, the study posits and answers the following research question:

1. How reliable is the vaccine cold chain network of Pakistan?
2. What, according to the stakeholders, are the issues impacting the reliability of the cold chain and what are some of their possible solutions?

Significance of the study

Studying immunization cold chains becomes immensely important once we observe the complexities involved with handling them, the impact they hold in terms of finances and

human lives everywhere in the world, and how they often suffer from neglect. If the maintenance is poor, a cold chain may easily render its vaccines impotent. A study conducting retrospective analyses of interruptions in the vaccine cold chain shows that such cold chain breakdowns can lead to immense financial losses which can be prevented through effective monitoring of vaccines, temperatures, equipment, and the continuous training of vaccine managers (Larena Fernández et al., 2017). Moreover, any analysis on cold chains should keep in mind that, beyond financial waste limitations, full and equitable immunization coverage can lead to many avoidable human deaths (Brison & LeTallec, 2017). According to one study's projections, immunization programs yield returns 16 times greater than the initial investment owing to how they enable people to live longer and healthier lives (Ozawa et al., 2016).

Evidence from research shows that the vaccine supply chain has not been given the required attention that it deserves. Lee and Haidari (2017) assert that despite the focus on developing new and better vaccines, failure to understand vaccine supply chains and address its problems can substantially affect the impact of any vaccine. Studies have shown that due to the multiple bottlenecks and constraints within the vaccine supply chain, many areas around the world are deprived of proper vaccines (Lee et al., 2015). Efforts to eliminate and control diseases such as polio and measles have been greatly hindered by the problems in the vaccine cold chains ("WHO | Immunization supply chain and logistics - A neglected but essential system for national immunization programs. A CALL-TO-ACTION", 2014). It is not just the less developed countries that suffers from these issues, there is also evidence of supply chain limitations in the developed world. Questions on vaccine cold chains therefore draw in concern from not only vaccinologists, vaccine package designers, and information system specialists but also policymakers who understand their importance and impacts (Lee and Haidari, 2017).

These findings highlight the significance of research on immunization cold chains. With the world going through the Covid19 pandemic and amidst the global efforts to provide the Corona vaccine, it then becomes pertinent for vaccination projects to analyze the cold chain and take it into consideration when planning and creating an immunization strategy.

Theoretical perspective

According to Prasad (2005), subjective interpretation to develop knowledge and understanding of the world lies at the heart of the interpretative tradition. He also placed emphasis on the multiple social dimensions of reality present in the interpretative tradition. This qualitative case study makes use of interpretive theoretical perspective to guide the data collection and analysis. Using the interpretive theoretical perspective adds a touch of philosophical richness and depth to our study as is the case with qualitative case study research (Jones, Torres, Arminio, 2006). Moreover, the interpretive approach allows us to capture the unique and complex interactions present in systems such as the vaccine supply chain. As a result, we are able to view the existing issues and problems from the point of view of the stakeholders present in the system.

List of Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this research study:

ASV: Assistant Superintendent Vaccination

EPI: Expanded Program on Immunization

DHO: District Health Officer

DDHO: Deputy District Health Officer

LHW: Lady Health Worker

BHU: Basic Health Unit

DHQ: District Health Quarter

THQ: Tehsil Health Quarter

ILR: Ice Liner Refrigerator

NVI: New Vaccine Introduction

POL: Petrol/Oil/Lubricants

Report overview

Chapter 1 introduced the research study as a whole. It outlined the problem statement and overviewed the background. It also outlined the study's purpose and significance, research questions and the theoretical perspective. Chapter 2 highlights the literature on the immunization cold chain network of Pakistan with a focus on the analysis of the network. Chapter 3 delves into the epistemological framework utilized in the study. At the same time, it mentions the research design, information regarding the participants, data collection and analysis methods, limitations and etc. Chapter 4 discusses the research findings while Chapter 5 talks about the implications, recommendations, and further discussions.

CHAPTER 2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous studies have been conducted to understand the challenges faced by Pakistan's cold chain system. However, these challenges still remain a point of concern for the government, policy makers and numerous other stakeholders. This review examines the current problems in cold chain of Pakistan. Specifically, it covers the existing research done on evaluating the cold chain and examines various possible interventions that can be implemented.

Immunization Cold Chain of Pakistan

The immunization cold chain of Pakistan is spread across its four provinces (Punjab, Balochistan, Sindh and KPK), Islamabad, Gilgit Baltistan and Azad Jammu & Kashmir. The number and kind of administrative levels, population, distribution of settlements, etc. are some of the factors which define the immunization cold chain practice and structure (*Immunisation Supply Chain Improvement Roadmap for Pakistan*, 2018). Following the traditional government administrative structure, the federal government is responsible for procuring vaccines from internationally. After entering the country through the Islamabad Airport, the vaccines are stored at the Federal EPI warehouses and then further distributed to the provinces. The provinces are further divided into generally 3 levels (District, Tehsil, and Union Councils), where each lower level is responsible for procuring vaccines from the level above it. Some districts also have an additional Division level to improve access to vaccines for health workers. From the EPI centers at the UC level, the vaccines are carried onsite by the vaccinators to be delivered to the citizens.

Image 2: Immunization cold chain of Pakistan. (Source: *Immunisation Supply Chain Improvement Roadmap for Pakistan*, 2018)

Existing Challenges in the Immunization Cold Chain of Pakistan

The World Health Organization (“WHO Expanded Programme on Immunization”, 1998) prescribes that cold chains should be evaluated based on three fronts: personnel, equipment, and procedures. Evaluation criteria include items relating to vaccine storage i.e., refrigeration maintenance and condition, temperature regulation and maintenance; and vaccine stock which includes quantity, wastage and reserves, record-keeping and monitoring.

However, the most significant factor for the proper performance of a cold chain system is the knowledge and practices of health personnel responsible for monitoring the cold chain. According to an article informed by Clinton Health Access Initiative's experience working with immunization partners and National Immunization Programs (NIPs) to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of Cold Chain and Logistics (CCL) systems, the vaccines' CCL system is stated to be working well when "(i) the full schedule of antigens is consistently available to serve the target population, (ii) in potent condition, (iii) at an affordable cost, and (iv) with a CCL network of sufficient capacity and reach to meet current and upcoming NIP goals (e.g., new vaccine introductions)" ("Immunization supply chain and logistics", 2020).

Pakistan's largest immunization program, Expanded Programme on Immunisation (EPI), was launched in 1977 by the World Health Organization (WHO) to limit the spread of childhood communicable diseases. This program represents major investments from the country over the years but even then, the progress to immunize against vaccine-preventable diseases has been slow. Goals such as those related to polio, neonatal tetanus, and measles elimination have not been met and the country has sub-optimal EPI performance in the delivery of routine immunization.

Some of the major issues in the vaccine delivery system that are highlighted in the literature are electricity outage, security issues, lack of skilled vaccinators, poor logistic management (for example having no backup vaccine carriers in case of power outages), gaps in monitoring and service delivery, low coverage of the vaccine in both NIDs (National Immunization Days) and otherwise, and poor quality of monitoring systems and data (Mushtaq et al., 2010).

Lack of proper planning is the foremost problem which further leads to logistical issues in the supply chain. A research conducted in the city of Rawalpindi found that inadequate planning led to the unavailability of vaccines in the region (Ilyas, Rahim & Latif, 2017). As a result, the availability of vaccines for rabies in the region was only 60-70% (Ilyas, Rahim & Latif, 2017). Another study in Hyderabad, in 2016, highlighted that the quality of mobilization activities for bringing people to immunization centers was suboptimal, especially in rural union councils and found detailed micro-planning to be absent (Pervaiz et al., 2017). These studies emphasize the need for better planning.

Another major problem is that of absence of temperature regulation which renders many vaccines impotent and going to waste. This is the case for Karachi where a study on incidence of rabies found, via National Institute of Health (NIH)'s department National Quality Control Laboratory, that the minimum potency requirement was not satisfied because the vaccines had no protection and the temperature requirement of 4 degrees Celsius was not satisfied as there were frequent power cuts without any backup (Parviz et al., 2004). In another study in Karachi, out of 803 different clinics, centers, and pharmacies, refrigerators and freezers were found only in 491 of them. Only 38.52% of refrigerators and 7.32% of freezers had the recommended temperatures shedding light on the meager state of affairs (Arsalan, Naqvi, Iqbal & Shakeel, 2014). Even if ice-lined refrigerators are available, their temperature may not be regulated as was highlighted in a study in Quetta (Buledi et al., 2017). While backup generator for cold chain maintenance can be functional 75-85% of the time, fuel availability being low i.e., 50-60% can render them useless contributing to the plight of temperature regulation (Ilyas, Rahim & Latif, 2017).

Even in cases where the infrastructure is available, lack of trained vaccinators means that the equipment and the vaccines are not properly utilised. A 2012 cross sectional study in Quetta found that despite the majority of the health staff having adequate knowledge i.e., how to maintain temperature charts and monthly records, there were weaknesses in the practice of cold chain maintenance (Buledi & et al, 2017). Lack of trained health workers directly involved in managing the cold chain translated into issues such as 30% of the staff incorrectly identifying measles and Bacillus Calmette-Guérin as cold-sensitive vaccines while many of them did not know how to use refrigerator seals and vaccine carriers despite availability in health centers (Buledi et al., 2017). Another study in 2016 showed how vaccinators, especially the ones in outreach stations, could have performed better if they were trained more rigorously in the pre campaign planning stage (Pervaiz et al., 2017). Thus, lower knowledge levels about the chains and its processes translates into sub optimal performance of the entire cold chain (Pervaiz et al., 2017). This issue is further exacerbated when they attempt to provide information to other uneducated people, and this results in the spread of misinformation about vaccines and cold chain systems beyond the first person.

All these factors have led to the failing of Pakistan's cold chain structure and immunization efforts as evident from the low and ineffective immunization coverage rates in the country. However, the issues in the cold chain system cannot be separated from the larger structural problems and can be attributed to them to a great extent. One such problem is that of equity. A paper from the Department of Paediatrics and Child Health, Agha Khan University argues that inequitable access to immunization, low demand, poor security, and social resistance have been major causes of the system's failings. Inequitable access to immunization is evident from vaccination coverage being 75% in Punjab and only 45% in Baluchistan and

FATA. Nationwide social inequality is also a result of local cultural beliefs, religious misconceptions, low literacy rates, and gender gaps. Low literacy rates result in knowledge gaps which result in low compliance to vaccination schedules (Mushtaq et al., 2010). Moreover, diseases such as typhoid are not only persistent due to absence of effective immunization coverage but also due to poor economic conditions including a lack of food hygiene and sanitation which are required to sustain health levels (Khan et al., 2006).

Constitutional and legal impediments have also caused a myriad of issues with Pakistan's immunization goals. The devolution of healthcare functions to the provinces has had adverse consequences as they have not been able to provide the necessary investments and attention to develop the required immunization infrastructure for proper vaccine delivery (Owais et al., 2013). Sania Nishtar adds more depth to the analysis of the issues with immunization coverage. She says that the country's health systems consist of an underfunded public sector and poorly regulated private sector coupled with low transparency in the government all of which diminish the performance of the sector substantially. Even if a program is well funded like that of Polio Eradication Initiative, public infrastructure through which it is delivered is underfinanced and in a poor state rendering the initiative helpless (Nishtar, 2010).

To make matters worse, despite the dire need for vaccines, Pakistan does not have an independent agency for regulating and maintaining vaccine quality and cold chains. The absence and dire need of an external vaccine monitoring agency to deal with critical public health challenges was highlighted in a study to estimate the incidence of rabies in Karachi and determine the effectiveness of post-exposure treatment (Parviz et al., 2004).

Lastly, some external and miscellaneous factors that limit the cold chain include vast variations in weather conditions and temperatures, large scale conflicts, and natural disasters that impact the vaccine supply chain (Khan & Ahmad, 2015). For example, interventions such as polio vaccination campaigns are banned in many areas of FATA for security reasons (Shakeel et al., 2019).

New vaccine introductions (NVI) as a part of an existing or new immunization campaigns (such as in the case of Covid19 vaccine) also face similar challenges. Like all low- and middle-income countries, the greatest challenge in introducing new vaccines within Pakistan is meeting the financial costs associated with these programs. In an already underfunded healthcare system, devoting resources towards new vaccines is quite challenging and imposes greater constraints on existing vaccination programs. Moreover, costs incurred for new vaccines often exceed the total budget devoted to immunization (Masud and Navaratne, 2012). Because of this, success of NVIs (New Vaccine Introductions) in Pakistan is largely dependent on support from foreign funding and international health organizations such as GAVI (Global Alliance for Vaccine and Immunizations) as highlighted in a study by the Health, Nutrition, and Population Family of the World Bank in 2012. The purpose of the study was to identify what level of support from GAVI would be required to optimally carry out NVI programs for PCV-10 (pneumococcal), Hib (Haemophilus influenza type B), and Rota-Teq (Rotavirus) vaccines (Brenzel, Sanderson, Galayda, Masud & Haq, 2011). Using estimates for future cold chain costs, projections were made on the financial implications of NVIs. The analysis revealed that without GAVI funding for up to 8 years, it was unlikely that the system would be able to bear the financial burden of the three vaccine programs. This was because the existing health budget was extremely inadequate and would not be able to bear the costs of

vaccines despite a predicted decrease in costs in the later years of the program (Brenzel, Sanderson, Galayda, Masud & Haq, 2011). This study was quite impactful as it helped the World Bank appreciate that even with 5 years of GAVI funding, it was unlikely that the health system of Pakistan would be able to bear the financial expenses of vaccination programs. Consequently, GAVI pledged to provide funding to Pakistan's pneumococcal vaccine program (which commenced in 2012) for 8 years.

Another factor which influences the success of NVI programs in Pakistan is the financial implication of 18th Amendment of the Constitution of Pakistan. Under this amendment, provincial governments were authorized to make decisions regarding new immunization programs in their region (Khan et al., 2014). Although this amendment was introduced in 2010, the transition from a federally operated healthcare system to a provincial one has been gradual and drawn out. Because of this, the financial impact of this amendment is still unfolding to this day. Masud and Navaratne (2012) identified that the health system of Pakistan was ill prepared to bear the financial expenses of NVIs on a provincial level (as proposed in the 18th amendment). According to the researchers, devolution of immunization programs to a provincial level would lead to a significant disparity in the level of funds available for immunization programs. This in turn would cause provinces to make budget commitments which would be impossible for them to keep. To cater to this problem the study proposed that provincial programs for new vaccines should only move forward once the federal government can confirm that provincial health departments have adequate budgets. Being among the first well rounded studies to address the implications of the devolution of health services to a provincial level, this study highlighted an important gap in existing literature, which is the disparity (amongst provinces) in resources available for new vaccine rollouts.

Although the cold chain infrastructure pertaining to new vaccine rollouts in Pakistan has improved over the last decade, the effectiveness of vaccine programs has not improved significantly. This is due to the fact that the cold chain infrastructure is not utilized effectively, and these inefficiencies remain unaddressed in existing literature. Firstly, the current literature fails to achieve a consensus on the best way to tackle inefficiencies that contribute to low coverage levels. Secondly, both policy makers and the health department are unable to conceive strategies that would allow for the introduction of new vaccines without hampering the progress of existing programs such as the polio vaccination campaign. Thus, future studies should address these factors so that future immunization campaigns are able to make the most of the current cold chain resources.

Another gap in the research related to both routine immunization and NVI is that it fails to incorporate the subjective view point of various stakeholders that are part of the system. The existing literature mainly makes use of quantitative analysis to evaluate the performance of the vaccination programs and the vaccine cold chain. This approach reduces the complex interactions and multifaceted problems to simple numbers and as a result fails to identify the underlying causes of these problems. Moreover, the studies conducted so far only tackle individual issues such as the maintenance of cold storage, vaccine coverage, etc. and lack a holistic approach.

This research aims to fill this gap by conducting a qualitative case study research as an exploratory effort into understanding the complex problems of the cold chain system of Pakistan. The research would further aim to evaluate the reliability of the cold chain through an in-depth investigation of the selected cases.

CHAPTER 3. METHODOLOGY

We chose a qualitative study for our research due to several reasons. According to Bogdan and Biklen (2003), qualitative approach is essential in understanding the meaning that people assign to their experiences and events. The purpose of this research study was to discover the meaning that stakeholders give to the complex events and challenges that they experience within the cold chain network.

A qualitative case approach is also appropriate when the aim of the research is to conduct an exploration (Stake, 1995). Our study was conducted as an exploratory research with the purpose to discover what is happening in the vaccine cold chain's domain in the country and generate new insights concerning the metric of reliability. To that end, we have tried to answer the following *what* questions: 1) to what extent is the vaccine cold chain of Pakistan reliable in its procurement, storage, delivery, etc. of the vaccines? 2) what are some of the challenges and issues experienced by the stakeholders that are impacting the reliability of the vaccine cold chain?

The qualitative research methods used in this study are semi-structured interviews and systematic data analysis. The study uses the case study approach to explore the domain of cold chain performance and challenges. Case study approach through its in-depth analysis, further allows the participants to share their detailed accounts.

Research Design

This research uses the case study approach as its methodology. Case study methodology has been defined as an in-depth inquiry of any event, individuals, program, process, etc. The phenomena being investigated here is the reliability of the vaccine cold chain of Pakistan and

the challenges by the stakeholders involved. The case for the current study is administrators involved in the cold chain network while the unit of analysis is the individual districts of Pakistan that are involved in the study.

Research Site

Due to the Covid19 pandemic, we had some trouble accessing the sites. We ended up choosing district Rawalpindi in the Punjab Province due to easy accessibility. Due to lack of access to potential stakeholders at the higher levels (provincial and federal levels), we had to limit our research to the district and its lower levels.

The research sites for this study were the various health units/departments in the district. These included District Health Authorities, Tehsil Health Quarters, Basic Health Units and EPI centers.

Participants

The participants for the study were the administrators at different levels of the district and lower health units. Purposeful sampling was used to select individuals on the basis of the value they could add in the form of information and insights regarding the cold chain network. The selection of health units was again based on how easily accessible they were depending on their location. Around 4 administrators were selected for interviews from each level of the districts. For the purpose of adding additional insights, some consultants and health experts with extensive knowledge and experience of working in the immunization programs were also interviewed.

Data Collection Method

Considering the scope of this research, interview was used as our data collection method. Interviews are an appropriate way to understand a phenomenon from someone else's point of view. As a result, using interviews suited well for our aim to understand the challenges faced by the stakeholders that are part of the cold chain network. Moreover, using qualitative interviews allowed us in getting detailed descriptions of the subjective experiences of the participants. This helped us in conducting an in-depth exploratory analysis of the subject at hand.

16 participants were interviewed between March – April 2021. All interviews were conducted via voice calls because of the travel restrictions imposed in light of the covid pandemic. In hindsight, conducting interviews over voice call helped us in gathering deeper insights due to 2 reasons. Firstly, the interviewees were able to openly share about their concerns and challenges due to the added factor of anonymity provided by voice calls. Secondly, since the interviews were conducted outside the office timings, interviewees were able to share information which they would not have felt comfortable sharing while being at their workplace. Each interview lasted around 30-45 minutes and was recorded after getting permission from the interviewee for accurate transcription. We also made handwritten notes during the process to track key points and discuss areas of interests.

The interviews usually began with our introductions. The participants were informed that the purpose of the study was to merely identify the challenges and issues in the cold chain network. Telling them about the purpose as evaluating the reliability of the cold chain might have produced biased responses from them. The participants were also assured of their confidentiality.

The semi-structured interview was conducted using a set of open-ended questions to obtain information regarding the performance of the cold chain on the metric of reliability (see Appendix for questionnaire). Questions related to operational efficiency were added later on as it was observed to be a major theme in the participants' responses. The participants were encouraged to respond freely to the open-ended questions. Follow up questions were asked wherever clarification of a response was required.

The transcription of the interviews started right after the interview process started and were completed by 21st April 2021.

Data Analysis

We treated the data analysis process as a creative exercise of creating meaning out of the data. Due to its continuous nature, we started analyzing our data as soon as our first interview was conducted. This allowed us to identify certain patterns and help in future data collection. Our qualitative data analysis followed the guidelines of Esterberg (2002) and Creswell (2009) who suggest identifying themes and categories of interest by getting intimate with the data and working intensively with it. After conducting all interviews and transcribing them, codes were generated using the open coding process on MAXQDA 2020 Pro. Various codes were then studied and grouped together into major themes. As the next step of the analysis process, the emergent themes were woven into a logical narrative and then interpreted for meaning.

Research Steps

Following steps made part of the research methods:

1. The participants were contacted and invited for an interview over voice call.
2. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with the participants over call.

3. Interviews were recorded and then transcribed for analysis.
4. The researchers reviewed and analyzed the transcribed interviews.
5. The data was coded to identify themes.

Researcher Positionality

Due to the important role of researchers as the main instrument of data collection in qualitative research, it is important for them to acknowledge their own biases, limitations, and views.

All the researchers are senior year students at Lahore University of Management Sciences (LUMS) enrolled in either BSc (hons) Management Sciences or BSc (hons) Accounting and Finance programs. One member of the team has a close relative who has worked in the health sector before. While the rest of the team members do not have any affiliations with the health sector which may have influenced their analysis of the subject at hand. Moreover, Similarly, only one member is a local of one of the two districts where the study was conducted.

Limitations

The study does not come without some limitations. Firstly, given the constraints and lack of access to documentary evidence, the current study is purely based on qualitative analysis. However, we believe that a mixed method study would have suited better to conduct an evaluation of the reliability of the cold chain structure. Relying on data sources other than semi-structured interviews such as on-site visits, documentary reports, etc. would have been helpful in triangulation of data and improving the reliability of our analysis.

Furthermore, the study was only conducted in a single district of Punjab. The demographics and population distribution in this district are some of the factors which impact the performance of its cold chain structure. As a result, a study conducted in this district alone might not apply to other areas of the country or the province which have drastically different population distributions and demographics. Similarly, our study is also limited to the lower administrative levels only. Conducting interviews of stakeholders at the provincial and/or federal level could have provided more in-depth understanding of the issues at hand. For example, it would be difficult to argue that these interviews can capture a full picture of budgetary constraints. Perhaps speaking to the ministry of finance and their provincial counterpart would be a good step in understanding the issues themselves better alongside possible contradictions in actual policy and its implementation.

CHAPTER 4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

The purpose of this research study was to explore how Punjab's vaccine cold chain performs on the metric of reliability in the views of the stakeholders present. The primary research question driving our research, as mentioned earlier, was how does Punjab's cold chain perform on the metric of reliability? Semi structured interviews were carried out to allow the participants to discuss their perceptions and experiences which varied given their role in the cold chain. The following research findings are based on the analysis of these semi structured, in depth interviews.

Background

A total of sixteen interviews were conducted for this exploratory research. The participants of this study included two external collaborators of the cold chain, one of them an instructor at LUMS who has previously researched on vaccine cold chains in the country, and the other an associate at Acasus, a leading consultancy organization working with the government of Pakistan to improve public healthcare. Since vaccine is procured and distributed from the country's capital, we interviewed two people on the federal level of the cold chain to understand their perspective, one of them working on VLMIS, the vaccine management system, and the other one person a part of the senior management of the Expanded Program on Immunization (EPI). Within the province of Punjab, our research was focused on one district only i.e., Rawalpindi where we interviewed twelve individuals present on the different levels namely district level, tehsil level and union council or the basic health unit (BHU) level to gain a thorough understanding of the cold chain's reliability from different viewpoints. A total four interviews were conducted on district level, five interviews were

conducted on tehsil level and three interviews were conducted on union council level. All of our participants were males except one.

To protect the identities of our participants, they were assigned pseudonyms. The key themes identified in our questionnaire to explore the metric of reliability were delivery delay, quality inadequacy and unqualified products and each of our interviewees provided different amount of information in these themes. All participants' views are represented in this study.

Study Findings

We had three key themes in our questionnaire as mentioned earlier. After the interviews were transcribed, we thoroughly read and reread the transcripts and labelled not only the key themes present in our questionnaire but also highlighted certain other themes. This entire process was performed in the software MAXQDA 2020 Pro. These other themes were identified using the criteria of relevance to our primary metric of reliability, significance as emphasized by the interviewee, repetition in several interviews, or having the element of surprise due to its unusualness. This marked the end of our initial coding process, after which the themes were rearranged to bring similar ideas together, so we eventually had the following themes:

1. Delivery delay
2. Unqualified product
3. Quantity inadequacy & procurement
4. End delivery
5. Managerial decisions

There was overlap between the themes and one answer from a participant may be contributing to multiple themes.

Theme 1: Delivery Delay

Within delivery delay existed several sub-themes namely emergencies, unreasonable vehicle scheduling and inventory shortage.

Emergencies

When probed about what sort of emergencies i.e., bad weather, traffic accident or vehicle breakdown resulted in delivery delays, all the stakeholders in Rawalpindi district's cold chain stated that emergencies did not result in delivery delays.

On the district level, Mr. SA termed the system as perfect and insisted that the vaccines are maintained from the federal level to the grassroots level through the use of ILRs (Ice Liner Refrigerators) as well as mobile carriers with gel packs. Dr. GI, also present on the district level, backed Mr. SA stating that there were two big vehicles present on district level which are available 24 hours with equipment to maintain cold chain as well as vaccine carriers with ice packs to maintain the temperature. He reassured that even if emergencies arise, standby vehicles are present as part of the contingency plan to avoid delivery delays.

On the tehsil level, The Assistant Superintendent Vaccination (ASV) NA backed his superiors' statement by stating that the cold boxes are firstly locked, secondly ice packs are strong and lastly cold boxes can easily hold vaccines for six hours eradicating the chances of vaccine being ruined by emergencies during travel. ASV MG unlike his colleague accepted the possibility of delivery delay occurring as a result of emergencies citing the example of lockdowns due to COVID resulting in delivery delays, however, he immediately added that throughout his service, such an incident had not occurred. Further, due to availability of mobile phones, easy flow of information now allows communications regarding the transport

of vaccine. There are protocols set in case of an emergency such as in the case of car accidents, employees are trained to prioritize the cold boxes and ensure the cold boxes' safety. The vehicle damage should not get priority and the employees are required to arrange private transport for the cold boxes first and then look after the vehicle. ASV KA also stated that there had been no emergencies in his experience however, if such a scenario arises, they have to inform the Drawing and Disbursing Officer (DDO) and then arrange something on urgent basis. While ASV AR did not shed light on whether such an occurrence had risen in his experience, he highlighted the need for a cold room vehicle on tehsil level so if there is some accident or traffic jam, instead of wastage of vaccination worth millions, a cold room vehicle would maintain vaccine temperatures for prolonged periods. To avoid facing emergencies, the staff travels very early in the morning when the roads are empty to avoid facing any accidents.

On the union council level, when the vaccinators were asked, Vaccinator TA stated that no emergencies had ever occurred during travel, however, if some sort of personal emergencies (health issues, etc.) do occur, there is no backup staff available so the children will not get vaccinated until or unless he himself reaches the destination safe and sound with the vaccine. In case any emergency situation happens while he is travelling to the tehsil to procure vaccine, he could easily inform them that he would not be able to make it. Vaccinator SA said that there was no contingency plan in case of any emergencies and if the weather conditions were unfavorable, the vaccination would get delayed to the next day. He added how he had never faced an emergency situation.

Unreasonable Vehicle Scheduling

These findings are further subdivided into route planning, inadequate delivery staff, inadequate transport vehicle.

Route Planning

Our external collaborators highlighted how important route planning is in the cold chain system. Mr. AK mentioned that once the federally procured vaccine reaches the federal EPI stores in Islamabad in Chak Shahzad next to the National Institute of Health (NIH), the vaccine cold chain logistics managers become in charge for distribution of the vaccine to the different provinces. For Gilgit Baltistan and Balochistan vaccines are taken via air. For Punjab cars arrive from Lahore and they pick up the vaccine which is taken to the two provincial stores in Punjab i.e., Manga Mandi (in Lahore) and Multan. The distribution works through Punjab's EPI which is responsible for distributing the vaccine to districts based on their annually calculated demand driven by their population size. The districts are asked to come to the stores and collect the vaccine. Once the vaccine arrives at the district, they're held at the district store for a very short time before they are sent out to the tehsils. From the tehsil level they go to the EPI center. Then they reach the health facility where the children who need to be vaccinated are present. Further, Ms. AS shed light on how important vehicle scheduling is because the vaccine is procured on federal level and then distributed to provinces and throughout this process it is transported from one warehouse to another and for this purpose, the government has made a dedicated workforce which is responsible for the vaccine transport from the highest level down to when it is administered to children. The entirety of process relies on effective route planning and ensuring the vehicle is there for pick up or delivery when needed.

The entire distribution within the district is inhouse as stated by Mr. AS, our source on district level. When inquired regarding the measures taken to ensure vehicles are travelling as scheduled, Dr. GI pointed out that all vaccines have bar coding which allows the vaccine to be identified and tracked from production till it reaches the end user. He also added that after the initial distribution by federal to provinces based on their demand, due to 18th amendment devolution of power to provinces, every province manages their vaccines themselves.

According to personnel on tehsil level, not a lot of planning is required and the process for vaccine transport is simple at this level. ASV MG said the district delivers the vaccine on one day notice once a month which lasts 40 days and their only task is to ensure cold boxes are ready when the vaccine arrives, no other prep is needed. From there, it takes about 5 minutes for them to take these boxes to the storage area where they place the vaccine in ice lined freezers. The next day the ASVs simply contact the vaccinators to come and get their vaccines to take them to fixed sites. Vaccinators have their own mobile carriers which they bring. An interesting fact mentioned here was how the vaccinators arrive in their personal conveyance to receive the vaccine as stated by ASV KA. In outreach programs, they again use their own transport to carry the vaccine to the site. Vaccinator TA mentioned how vaccinators only go to receive the vaccine after the day's planned vaccination is completed because otherwise children would miss their vaccinations and 'default'. Vaccinator AT mentioned how it takes up a complete day just to get the vaccines because it takes time to get their turn. The ideal way according to him would be that a proper vehicle should carry vaccines till the BHU level. This would improve the cold chain system.

Once the vaccine has been received on UC level, Vaccinator AT shed light on the next steps as: 'We make a plan for the next 6 months and for that we already take permission from

the local people whose place/house we are going to use for the monthly visits. And most of the time, other local people are aware of this particular location and the time and day on which the vaccinators are supposed to visit, so they reach there on their own. The Lady Health Workers (LHWs) if they are present in the area, also spread awareness regarding these visits by the vaccination staff. When we have to visit this site, first we go to the Tehsil Health Quarter (THQ) or the BHUs and get our required vaccines after registering on the stock register. Then we go to the field. We have a fixed date to visit each village in an area. Once in an area, we make an announcement from the mosque or from a house of some local person and ask the people to come and get their children vaccinated. We stay there till around 1 pm. We have a mobile application through which we have to check in and check out on a location. The vaccination details are entered in a daily register and then we take it back to the THQ or BHU. The data from the daily register is then copied on to the permanent register. And the extra vaccine is then put in return box. These vaccines are used first for the future daily tasks. If more vaccines are required then they need be registered from stock. Apart from that, there is even a room in the THQ where people can come and get vaccinated if they were not able to get the vaccines when the vaccinator visited their area.'

There were some issues in route planning highlighted on every level which are discussed ahead. According to Mr. KA, due to unreasonable route planning, districts in Punjab such as Rawalpindi, Attock, Chakwal have to officially go to Lahore to get their vaccines even if they were located closer to the federal store in Islamabad. This resulted in 4-5 days delay and vaccines stocking out on tehsil level. Thus, people are unofficially now, especially in times of COVID, moving the vaccine directly from Islamabad to Rawalpindi but officially, the government requires otherwise. This issue was also highlighted by Mr. IS who is working on

district level in Rawalpindi. He stated that while it is best for them that their vaccine is issued directly from Islamabad, sometimes they have to go to Lahore to get their vaccine. He stated there is a major room for improvement in managing routes because while Rawalpindi mostly gets its vaccine directly from Islamabad, districts like Chakwal, Attock, Jhelum still don't get their vaccines directly from NIH causing delays and wastage of resources.

Inadequate delivery staff

Dr. AS, our external researcher, stated that from her experience of studying vaccinators, she found some of them to be very irresponsible which broke the cold chain often. They stored the vials sometimes in thermoses or dry packs and while the rural health centers have freezers in which vaccines are placed, the people managing those places are often complacent. However, she also sometimes found incredibly committed people who were very particular about maintaining the cold chain. Her conclusion was that the system is not consistent enough because sometimes even these responsible people do not get the help they require; even if they inform their supervisors regarding the help required, the supervisors simply inform his own supervisors and eventually nothing comes out of it resulting in a lot of inconsistencies and management issues in the vaccine cold chain.

It was found that there is an understaffing issue of vaccinators almost everywhere as stated by Mr. KF, our Rawalpindi district source. He also added: In Islamabad we have an EPI project till June 2021 and we foresee that all the EPI staff currently on contract with us for this project will become permanent with us if this project becomes permanent. However, if project is not continued or regularized then we will face an understaffing issue.

Our source on the federal level, Mr. AN, explicitly mentioned “We have shortage of technical trainings and trained staff. We find very few expert people.” However, our senior source on district level, Mr. SA denied this when asked “Is there ever an issue with the availability of human resources especially when vaccine demand is greater?”

The understaffing issue was also highlighted by the ASVs. A UC relies heavily on the presence of a vaccinator. According to ASV KA, there is only one vaccinator in every UC ward while in the fixed site, there is medical administrator and a vaccinator so even if vaccinator is unavailable, it is the medical administrator’s duty to ensure vaccinations.

ASV MG mentioned two UCs which were unable to operate because they were empty due to a lack of staff. According to him, this shortage of vaccinators is because sometimes people who pass the course are not willing to go to a secluded area to work. Another issue is that sometimes people pass the course but are unable to meet the government requirements because the government has special policies in place about where people should be appointed. We have to wait for the government to be able to approve appointments even if people are willing and available to work. These factors add to shortage of staff. He also mentioned a shortage of lady health workers who would be especially helpful to gather people at site and make parents comfortable during their children’s vaccination. ASV AR also mentioned how other vaccinators have to cover up for the vacant position till it is filled.

Vaccinators also highlighted the shortage of delivery staff. Vaccinator SA mentioned how if the vaccinator was ill, the entire vaccination schedule and plan was delayed as there is no backup available. Vaccinator TA also spoke on the issue of lack of delivery staff especially lady health workers:

I have to administer vaccines in 11 different localities. I only have four lady health workers to assist me in this. These four workers are only available in the first few days of the month that I visit. The problem with this is that there are several stations in which I have to administer vaccines but do not have any lady health workers. A lot of families have issues with having their children vaccinated without lady health workers being present due to cultural norms. Ideally for these 11 localities there should be 16 lady health workers to help assist. Because of absence of a lady health worker sometimes we have to shift the station to a place where both the lady health worker and families can access. I have two male employees to assist me but they do not accompany me usually. But even in this case, the staff available to me is only present for the first few days of the month and for all other days I am usually the only one working for the outreach vaccinations.

Inadequate transport vehicle

While we were at one of the offices for conducting an interview with Mr. IS in Rawalpindi district office, we firsthand saw the issue of unavailability of transport vehicles arising. The districts vehicle was gone to the tehsils to deliver vaccines and the district had to send vaccines to Lahore after picking it up from NIH but didn't have any vehicle for that. To resolve this, they eventually requested Attock for their vehicle and used it to transport the vaccines. Mr. IS later confirmed that they were working with low resources and added, "If there were two vehicles with reasonable capacity instead of one, then it would be the ideal situation as we could use one for supplying vaccines from district to tehsils and the other to procure vaccines from the province or the federal level. Especially right now, we have to use it for COVID related tasks and normally we have to pick the vaccines from Lahore. So, if the vehicle

goes for that, then it is not available for 24 hours.” Our federal source, Mr. AN stated that his team is trying to increase cold chain vehicles for transportation.

Another problem highlighted was the limited availability of vehicles at district level which makes it difficult to provide vaccines at the UC level. Mr. IS highlighted how the vehicle at the district level delivers the vaccine to each tehsil once a month, except for the rural Rawalpindi since there is no setup to store vaccines at the tehsil level. He added: “Instead we deliver the vaccine to 3-4 other places there. From the tehsils, the individual vaccinators or the ASVs then shift the vaccines in cold boxes to the UC level. This is since we don’t have a system or vehicle to shift the vaccines to the UC level. So here as well, there is some room for improvement. If we have 2-3 vehicles at the district level, then we can even provide vaccines at the UC level.

ASVs had a general consensus that a presence of vehicle at tehsil level could improve transport situation. ASV KA mentioned how transport could be improved if there was a vehicle available at tehsil level to transport to UC level. ASV NA stated how there were no vehicles available for transport at tehsil level and it gets difficult when they had to dispatch vaccines to multiple hospitals at the same time. In such circumstances, he mentioned how they have to manage it with much difficulty using cold boxes lined with ice packs managing transport using their personal resources or public transport. ASV MG stated that if they have to use their own transport to procure the vaccines from the district, they use Deputy District Health Officer’s (DDHO) car whose fuel is paid by the office and it is uncommon for them to use their personal vehicles for procuring the vaccine from district office.

ASV AR also mentioned the use of DDHO's car to transport the vaccine from the district to tehsil since there is no official vehicle. He highlighted that there was no proper mechanism in place for such things and the system is running God willing. He emphasized how the DDHO's vehicle is often unavailable which results in many problems and then they have to borrow a friend's or someone else's vehicle and pay for the fuel themselves. He stated a pickup truck or Suzuki, which can fit cold boxes, is direly needed since district hardly provides any vehicle for procuring vaccines for the tehsil level. He added how they cannot afford to delay the delivery even if there is a storm or a tornado so they have to use any means necessary to get the vaccine on time.

ASV AZ had similar statements as he said "We have to use our own vehicle to send the boxes (vaccine carriers) to get the vaccine from the district which is very difficult. At Tehsil level, there is a car, perhaps a Suzuki, needed direly with cold room to bring the vaccines from district level here and further transport them easily. Until or unless we get a vehicle for work, why would anyone pay to refuel our personal motorcycles which we have been using for department's work?"

As mentioned earlier, vaccinators are using their own fuel for not only procuring the vaccines but also carrying them outreach sites and there is no vehicle available to ensure that the vaccine reaches the end of the cold chain safely, as discussed by Mr. KA. He further mentioned that the government is aware of the issue and agrees that there should be proper vehicles to carry the vaccine that also monitor the temperature but they will never give them the money because the government wants that they get the money from initiatives like GAVI or World Bank to hire and buy these cars that can distribute vaccines at the tehsil level. This is part of the plan that EPI is working on and this is partially EPI's responsibility because EPI is

heavily funded and they get a lot more money than any other program. They do try to arrange for cold room vehicles but it is difficult to convince donors too that they give them that kind of money. He added that at least for the next year he doesn't see any progress on this and while there have been discussions regarding this, there hasn't been any major progress per se on receiving vehicles.

Vaccinators seem to suffer the most as a result of inadequate transport vehicles and all of them mentioned the same issues. ASV MG mentioned how vaccinators have been given motorcycles but their conveyance allowance has been cut down. These vaccinators have to travel two to three hours to get these vaccines to rural areas, with no one paying for their fuel. Vaccinator TA mentioned how the fuel allowances by government were never even paid:

As per government policy we are allotted 15 liters of petrol each month. And in UCs which have mountainous terrain it is supposed to be 25 liters. But it is my fourth year in this job and I haven't been given a single rupee for these expenses and because of this I have been paying for fuel out of my own pocket even though the government is supposed to be the one paying for it. Secondly, we have been given motorcycles and WHO provides allowance for the maintenance of these vehicles. But we are not given any sort of the reimbursement for the maintenance of these vehicles and have to bear these expenses ourselves too. Earlier we used to be given a budget for conveyance but that has been cut down as well by around 32 rupees.

Vaccinator SA agreed with his colleague and recounted the same issues: Yes. We have been given motorcycles by the government but the government does not provide any running expenses. We have to incur the cost of fuel, maintenance, and the government has even cut

down on our conveyance allowance with the excuse that we have been provided bikes even though that allowance is supposed to cover day-to-day costs. Vaccinator AT also had the same experience with no petrol charges paid in the last 2 years which was more troublesome since his UC is a hilly area and his transport charges are doubled. He added how the vaccinators send the government twice yearly bills but they still don't receive the reimbursement. He further elaborated, "If our pay is 28,000 PKR then around 8000 PKR is spent on petrol. Some people get it. In my 5 years of service, I got it around 2-3 times. But it has been a year since I last got it. At the same time, we aren't given conveyance allowance. The bike that is being given to us is just for field work. Instead, if we are given monthly allowance, we can use that money to pay installments on the bike and it would be eventually our own property. Also, we aren't compensated for any maintenance that is required. So, we want the petrol allowance to be adjusted in our pay or directly transferred into our account." He stated how the vaccinators had no clue if their bills were passed to the government or simply ignored by the higher ups due to corruption; he said that vaccinators are unaware of the process. To make it worse, he mentioned how they used to get phone allowance, but since last month, their numbers had been blocked and they had been using their own money to send reports etc. He concluded how the job is very stressful since the pay is already meagre. But regardless, they have to work. However, they can't take ownership of the work and cannot put in their full energy.

Inventory Shortage

These findings are further subdivided in the following categories: replenishment delay and insufficient warehouse space.

Replenishment delay

Most of our interviewees stated that there were hardly ever vaccine shortages before the pandemic and one vaccinator SA even commented how they would get vaccine in excess of the demand. However, recently due to COVID and unforeseen circumstance, vaccinator SA and AT, Mr. KA, from Acasus, and Dr. GI, from district admin, recounted the shortage of Pentavalent vaccine right at the beginning of the pandemic for 2-3 months due to closure of flights. Mr. AK also confirmed the shortage of rotavirus vaccine which lasted a month but he did not recall the reason for it. 30% shortage of rotavirus vaccine was mentioned by Mr. IS in district admin. Dr. GI mentioned the use of buffer stocks in provincial level to manage the shortage. In case of extended shortages like in case of Pentavalent vaccine, consequently lesser amount is given to provinces and in turn, eventually the vaccinator, as highlighted by Mr. IS and vaccinator SA as even the buffer stocks ran out for Pentavalent vaccine. The vaccinators then mark these children, who do not receive the vaccine on time. Vaccinator SA further stated that otherwise no vaccine shortages had occurred and even if the vaccine is used more than demand, buffer stock is available as well as extra vaccine is available on tehsil level. This problem of shortage and delays is managed by the federal government.

Insufficient warehouse space

All vaccines are stored in ILRs on tehsil and UC level so a shortage of these automatically means a shortage of storage space. At district and provincial level, they are stored in cold rooms. Our source at federal level informed us that total capacity available at federal level is 3 lac 24,000 liters for 2 to 8 degrees Celsius, 1 lac 6,000 liters for -16 to -25

degrees, 6000 liters for ultra-cold chain ranging -75 to -85 degrees Celsius, most of which are Pfizer and rest 5 are Haier equipment installed with capacity 828 liters per equipment.

When Mr. AK was inquired regarding rating the whole system as an outsider, he mentioned the storage space at district level as having major room for improvement. However, according to Mr. IS working on district level there is 'enough space' as there are 2 cold rooms at the district level which can store 2 month's stocks so essentially at district and provincial level there is no shortage of storage space. According to him the shortage exists on tehsil and UC level; he mentioned the unavailability of cold rooms at the tehsil level resulting in lesser capacity to store the vaccines and therefore the vaccines have to be directly shifted to UC level. According to him it would be 'ideal to have cold rooms at the tehsil level.'

Mr. IS mentioned that around 10% of their ILRs were defected and it was important for an alternative solution to be implemented to this defective equipment. Coupled with this, about 15-20 of each district's ILR have been given to the recently formed covid centers, which weren't given ILRs of their own, resulting in a shortage of ILRs for EPI. As a result, the vaccines for 2 UCs are stored at a single place as there is no longer any availability of separate ILRs. Further these ILRs have to be placed in government schools or in UC offices due to shortage of health facilities. Due to lack of ILRs on tehsil and UC level, Mr. IS mentioned how in a recent campaign for TCV (typhoid conjugate vaccine) all vaccines couldn't be issued in a single go. So, the vaccines were kept at the district store and then issued for around 4 days each time. Further, these ILRs given for COVID vaccines would also prove to be insufficient as the vaccine quantity coming to the country increases in the future. So overall, there is a dire need for more ILRs and cold rooms at tehsil level according to him. Need for more ILRs and cold room at tehsil level was also expressed by ASV NA, AR and KA. In case of extended electricity

outage, according to ASV AR, they would have no choice but to take the vaccine all the way to the district headquarters for storage due to absence of cold rooms on tehsil level. ASV AZ also commented on the poor performance of ILRs as according to him, these had been damaged and repaired at least 4-4 times so their performance isn't the same as it was earlier and even though he highlighted this problem to senior administration and requested for 4 freezers and 12 ILRs, even after 1.5 years, he had gotten nothing.

When we inquired our source at district level Dr. KF and at federal level, Mr. AN, regarding the possibility of cold rooms at tehsil level, they both said there was insufficient demand for cold rooms to be installed at tehsil level. AN further explained, "Cold room's capacity minimum is 10 cubic and 1 cubic is equal to 1000 liter. Tehsil's demand is way lower than minimum cold room's capacity so cold rooms will always be on district or provincial level. For instance, provincial stores further distribute at district levels. Here cold rooms and freezer rooms both are available. Then further down at tehsil and health facility level we have ILRs which have different capacities such as 120 liters or 90 liters or 60 liters, products of B-medical and Haier, and they provide sufficient capacity to cover routine immunization. They can easily cover up routine vaccine as well as COVID vaccine and polio vaccine. All campaigns are also covered by these ILRs."

Mr. AN did seem to recognize the shortage of ILRs as a pressing issue as he mentioned efforts to increase capacity for instance getting about 3000 ILRs, 89 cold rooms and freezer rooms, 6500 vaccine carriers and cold boxes to further strengthen our cold chain. According to him the more major issues are equipment related for instance compressors are expensive and unavailable in Pakistan.

ASV NA showed us an interesting insight regarding the usage of new ILRs in the cold chains. With increased usage of ILRs, the staff cannot freeze ice packs in the available ILRs as ILRs temperature stays between +2 to +6 degrees. There is no mechanism for freezing ice packs apart from utilizing some old ILRs or freezing ice packs in their homes or local's homes. These ice packs are extremely important as they used to line vaccine carriers during transport of the vaccine. Vaccine may have to be transported due to ILR malfunction, long electricity outages i.e., 8-12 hours (ILRs can only last 4-6 hours without the electricity so transport to a nearby healthy facility becomes inevitable). This absence of freezers issue was also pointed out by ASV KA and AZ, which according to them are very important at BHUs and fixed sites. According to ASV AZ, this problem had been persistent for 6-7 years now.

The vaccinators seemed to have a consensus on the new ILRs having sufficient space for storage on UC level; according to vaccinator TA, there is plenty of space in the ILR and they only bring a quantity of vaccines that is needed so they always have space inside the ILR even after some buffer stock which is usually 20 additional vaccines. Vaccinator AT also expressed similar views.

Theme 2: Unqualified Products

Unqualified vaccines are those which either lose their potency or become completely wasted due to failure of the supply chain. There are a number of ways in which this can transpire. Specifically, our research showed that vaccine potency tends to be compromised as a result of Transport Damage, Warehousing Damage, or Packaging Processing Damage. Overall, we discovered that unlike other factors that affect reliability, there were adequate protocols in place at all levels of the supply chain to ensure vaccines remained effective.

Transport Damage

Due to the fragile nature of vaccine vials and the fact that vaccines need to be maintained within a fixed temperature range, damage during transit is a significant concern. To understand how reliable the transportation of vaccines is, it is important to first understand how vaccine are transported between different levels of the supply chain.

After vaccines have arrived at the Federal EPI Store in Islamabad, they are then distributed to individual provinces. In case of Punjab, this phase of transportation takes place in vehicles which have ILRs installed within them. Transportation from the Provincial to the Tehsil level also takes place in vehicles. However, these vehicles do not have ILRs installed within them and therefore vaccines are placed inside cold boxes lined with ice packs. At the Tehsil level, vaccines are given directly to vaccinators who place them inside their mobile carriers which are then used in each subsequent stage of transportation, until the vaccines are administered.

Our interviews revealed that the incidence of transport damage to vaccines is quite rare at both the federal and provincial levels. All vehicles are fully air conditioned and have

equipment installed to monitor and control the temperature of vaccines. One issue that came forward in the interview with Dr AN is that the introduction of COVID vaccine has placed a constraint on the number of vehicles available for transport. However, Dr AN revealed that so far, this had not caused any vaccines to get damaged, and that more vehicles are now being added to strengthen the cold chain.

At the district level, Dr IS revealed that there had been issues related to transport damage in the past, which resulted in the wastage of some dilutant containers. However, even in this case, there was no impact on the vaccines and the transport process was modified from then on to ensure dilutants were transported separately. Our research did reveal that there is a time constraint on the delivery of vaccines from the provincial to the district level as cold boxes can generally preserve vaccines for up to 8 hours only. Fortunately, the stores in Manga Mandi and Multan are positioned strategically so that transportation time to all districts is significantly less than 8 hours. Moreover, Dr GI stated that all vaccines have data logger tags installed on them that can be plugged into a PC to view the vaccine temperatures throughout the journey as well.

At the Tehsil and UC levels, the cold chain becomes less reliable due to a lack of proper equipment. There are no carriers designed for transporting vaccines on bikes, rather the vaccinators are expected to place the vaccines inside their mobile carriers and strap them onto their body as they travel from the tehsil to UC level and then to individual communities as well. All the vaccinators revealed that this mechanism of transport, (although not ideal), does result in the maintenance of the vaccine cold chain. The risk in this method is that carriers can often collide with vehicles or surrounding traffic which is not ideal. Vaccinator AT revealed this risk increases considerably when a vaccinator is expected to carry multiple carriers on their bike.

Vaccinator SA recalled an instance where the strap on his mobile carrier broke causing it to fall in the middle of the road. However, the carrier and the gel packs inside successfully cushioned the vaccines causing them to remain unharmed. Vaccinator AT also revealed that the ice packs can sometimes cause vaccine temperature to fall too far, causing vaccines to freeze which renders them unusable. This is a significant cause of vaccine wastage in winters and the discarded vaccines have to be written off as unusable. However, AT revealed that such instances can easily be avoided by allowing ice packs to catch some humidity before being placed inside of carriers.

Warehousing Damage

Prior to being administered, vaccines are stocked in warehouses situated all over the country. Federal warehouses are present in Islamabad while the provincial ones are situated in Manga Mandi near Lahore and in Multan. Vaccines in the 2 latter warehouses are distributed and subsequently stored in district level warehouses. Here the process of distribution and storage is repeated for tehsil level warehouses. In the last stage, tehsil level vaccines are divided among UCs and stored in health centers located in hospitals or in BHUs.

As vaccines spend an abundant amount of time in storage, any malfunction at this stage of the cold chain can result in the wastage of vaccines. Our preliminary research showed that issues in vaccine storage typically encompass three major areas of concern. These are vaccine cold storage power and standby power failure, cold storage monitoring equipment failure, and cold storage cooling equipment failure.

Similar to other themes, our interviews revealed that there is a stark difference between the maintenance of the cold stores at different levels of the cold chain. As we move down the supply chain, both the risks and incidence of malfunctions in warehouses increase.

At the federal and provincial level, warehouses are in pristine condition. Dr AN revealed that these warehouses have an adequate volume of ILRs available that can store vaccines without power for up to 12 hours. Power outages at this level are non-existent as warehouses have backup generators installed to ensure cooling equipment is not compromised. Moreover, there are data loggers on vaccines which record the vaccine temperature throughout the cold chain as well. According to Dr AN, even at the Union Council level such issues rarely take place as ILRs do not get damaged easily.

Dr AN also revealed that since the 18th Amendment, the federal EPI is not directly responsible for the maintenance and funding of warehouse management. However, since the program is vertical, Federal EPI does act as a means of communication between lower levels of the cold chain and UNICEF to ensure any warehousing issue is dealt with swiftly. Interestingly, Federal EPI employees do not have direct contact with Tehsil and UC level employees. Rather, provincial employees are expected to routinely monitor these warehouses and report issues and discrepancies back to the Federal EPI office.

At the district level, we received conflicting responses from different interviewees. Dr SA reiterated throughout the interview that the cold store setup at both the district level and other levels underneath it was perfect. He revealed that there are contingencies in place to cater to issues such as power outages, but such issues do not take place. Moreover, he remained

adamant that there is adequate availability of resources at every level of warehousing which he described as being perfect with no room for improvement.

In comparison, other interviewees felt that while the performance of cold stores was satisfactory, there were some glaring irregularities in the system which contributed to vaccine wastage. Dr GI revealed that warehouse damage is always a concern due to human errors and equipment malfunction, however there are always contingencies in place. ILRs can malfunction at times, but the district superintendent is wary of such breakdowns and can contact either the manufacturers of these ILRs or relevant staff at the provincial level, so they are fixed. Dr IS revealed that staff present in warehouses has to monitor and record the temperature of ILRs throughout the day. If an ILR is unable to maintain the temperature of a vaccine within the required range an alert is generated to the province as well.

When asked about power outages, Dr IS revealed that there are generators in place to take over. In case a generator also fails to work vaccines can be temporarily shifted to another cold room running on a different generator. He recalled an incident when rain caused electricity wires to snap, causing an outage to one of the cold rooms. Even in this case, all vaccines were timely shifted to a different room whilst repairs were performed. Thus, it is very unlikely for vaccines to be damaged during storage at the district level. All the same, there are protocols in place to ensure the potency of vaccines is not compromised. Vaccines are subjected to a shake test. The results of this test can reveal if a vaccine was frozen at any point during the cold chain. In such a scenario, the vaccine gets discarded. Moreover, vaccines are also observed for damage during loading/unloading. Such damage is easily identifiable and takes place occasionally. However, Dr GI revealed that all stores are granted a 10% wastage limit for every vaccine type. However, in truth the damage is rarely this extensive.

At the tehsil level, gaps in warehouse storage become more prominent. Almost all ASVs reported issues pertaining to power outages. The information provided to us by these ASVs contradicted that which was reported by Dr AN at the Federal level when he informed us that all Tehsils have adequate backups in the form of generators. The ASVs reported that very few Tehsils had backup generators. ASV NA stated that in case of power outages, vaccines remain stored in ILRs which can keep the temperature maintained for 10-12 hours depending on the season. ASV MG revealed that when power outages are prolonged vaccines are shifted to larger cold boxes which are lined with ice packs. There is a committee in charge at the DHO level which is informed of such an incident. The committee then has the vaccines transported to a neighboring DHO or a nearby tehsil warehouse with adequate space. However, all ASVs were in consensus that there are always contingencies to ensure power outages do not lead to wastage.

Similar negative reviews were provided regarding the maintenance of cold chain equipment. ASV KA revealed that many of the ILRs currently present do not function. He also expressed how there were a lack of freezers in the warehouse which meant that they were unable to freeze icepacks for use in BHUs and fixed sites. ASV AR also had similar reservations regarding the quality of equipment available to the Tehsil. In his opinion, the equipment was not maintained properly and took a long time to fix. The ASV also voiced concern that ILRs which had previously been allotted to the warehouse for emergency purposes, had now been taken away for use in the COVID supply chain. His concern was that this might cause a significant increase in vaccine wastage once the summer season commenced. But the most unsettling insight we obtained was from ASV AZ who stated that in case of cold chain equipment failure, workers at the tehsil and UC level have to pitch in to pay for the repairs. The

department does offer to repair the equipment but expects the tehsil employees to have the equipment transported to them out of their own pockets.

In comparison, all ASVs were positive about the reliability of monitoring equipment and protocols. ASV NA revealed that there is no system to automatically flag an alert in case temperature drops, however, the staff is able to handle monitoring manually. Throughout the day, both the stock and temperature of vaccines is noted down. This record is uploaded on the database which can be accessed by scanning the tags present on vaccines. Moving data for up to 2 months is available on the database. ASV KA stated that vaccine vial monitors are the most reliable way of monitoring vaccines. VVMs are present on all vials and tend to change colors depending on the stage of vaccine potency they are at. Once the color changes beyond a particular shade the vaccines are unusable. ASV AR also iterated those employees who are responsible for monitoring vaccines rarely slack off as they can be held accountable if the VVMs indicate any incompetence on their part.

At the UC level, irregularities in warehousing exceeded those observed at the tehsil level. We had already learned from Dr GI that UC level health centers tend not to have backup generators, rather there are UPS installed which can continue to power ILRs for some time. In most cases this can be enough to cater to power outages, however, in some UCs power outages are more frequent and longer. Dr AN revealed that such UCs are provided with ILRs that run on solar power. The vaccinators revealed that in case of issues such as transformer breakdowns they have to contact WAPDA directly and inform them that vaccines need to be maintained. In the meantime, the vaccines are either kept stored in ILRs or transported to nearby UCs. However, such contingencies can fail as well. Dr AS revealed that tehsil and district level employees are often unresponsive to such issues because of which UC employees take it upon

themselves to store the vaccines by taking them to their home refrigerators. Moreover, Vaccinator SA recalled an incident a few years prior when vaccines in his UC were wasted as a result of a transformer exploding. There were no WAPDA officials available for 2-3 days on account of Eid ul Adha. This particular UC had no UPS system in place either.

The UC employees did not feel there were any issues with monitoring the vaccines as all of them felt comfortable with the use of VVMs and its pertaining protocols. Moreover, no issues were reported regarding the maintenance of cold chain equipment, although Vaccinator AT admitted that there was an over reliance on use of ice packs because the ILRs at UC level do not store vaccines for as long as new ILRs can.

Packaging Processing Damage

Poor packaging is an important concern for any cold chain as defects in packaging can create issues in the monitoring and maintenance of the supply chain. In case of the vaccine supply chain, improper packaging material and improper protocols regarding the handling of vaccine packages during loading and unloading are important concerns. Since vaccines are loaded/ unloaded at various points during the cold chain there is always risk of damage to vaccine products.

In the initial stages of the cold chain (federal and provincial levels) vaccine vials are packed into large rectangular packages. In case of many tehsils, these vaccines are delivered in the same form to the tehsil warehouses. However, depending on the demand of a particular Tehsil, these packages may be opened in which case Tehsils are provided with individual vials instead. From the Tehsil level onwards, vaccines are transported inside these sealed vials, until they are to be used.

Our findings indicate that vaccine wastage due to improper loading/unloading is an important concern. As per Dr GI there is a 10% wastage limit for each type of vaccine at the district level for precisely this reason. However, this limit is precautionary because the store managers are quite competent at avoiding any form of damage to the vaccines. Similarly, UC level employees revealed that they tend to have extra vials in case of such emergencies, but the vaccinators know how to handle vaccines so there are rarely any wastages due to improper handling.

Employees at all levels of the cold chain were also in agreement that the material used to package vaccines is satisfactory and does not deteriorate over time. Dr IS revealed that in his career, he has never encountered any issues with vaccine packaging. Moreover, AK from Acasus informed us that larger Vaccine packages have tags installed within the packaging that record data on the temperature of vaccines. In this manner, vaccine packaging enables employees to monitor vaccine quality closely.

Vaccinator SA revealed that vaccine delivered to UCs are packaged in sealed vials which can have anywhere between 10 to 50 vaccines inside a vial (depending on the type of vaccine). However, the ASV revealed that ideally these vials should be placed in zip lock bags before being placed inside carriers. However, this is often not the case. Dr AS conveyed that while the vaccine packaging itself is up to standard, improper handling can damage the packaging. In particular, she stated that in case of power failure, UC and Tehsil level employees remove the vaccines from ILRs and place them in freezers in their home. This can cause the labels on vaccines to become wet and when this happens these labels can easily peel off.

Theme 3: Quantity Inadequacy

Vaccines are distributed to each level of the supply chain on a monthly or quarterly basis depending on the level of supply chain. This helps avoid unnecessary holding costs and loss in potency of vaccines. However, the trade off to this is that the risks of vaccine stock outs throughout the supply chain increase immensely. To counter any such event, employees at every level of the vaccine cold chain keep track of vaccine usage in their department.

In Pakistan, an information system called VLMIS is used to keep track of the level of vaccines present at every level of the cold chain. This system allows greater visibility in the cold chain inventory. Data is regularly fed into this software by employees present at UC, Tehsil, District, and Provincial levels. Based on this data, forecasts are prepared for subsequent months, and vaccines are distributed to all levels of the supply chain from these forecasts.

According to Mr. AK from Acasus, provincial government is responsible for the distribution of vaccines to individual districts. Since provincial forecasts are based on data recorded at subsequent stages of the cold chain, it is imperative that the process of recording and reporting data is carried out accurately. According to Dr. AN, this is a very smooth process as provincial and federal employees can access the VLMIS software at any time to view up to date figures on any type of vaccine. Moreover, a similar software has been developed specifically for COVID vaccines as well.

The provincial office in Lahore prepares vaccine estimates based on targets submitted by each district. These targets are consolidated into a report along with other key information such as number of vaccines received in prior month, vaccine balance, number of children successfully vaccinated, number of children in default, etc.

Each district prepares their own forecasts as well. According to Dr. SA, each district performs an annual audit of vaccine inventory present at the district store and prepares forecasts for future vaccine demand from the DDHO office (tehsil level). Dr. SA stated that the system is flawless as there are no discrepancies within the system.

Dr. GI revealed that data available on VLMIS is compared to predetermined targets which have been set for various antigens. Targets for children under 2 years, pregnant women, polio drives, and other programs is closely monitored. In case, there is any tehsil which has utilized most of its vaccine, employees at the district level can raise a flag to see why this was the case and stock is provided to the tehsil according to updated estimates.

At the Tehsil level, ASVs revealed that they are allotted vouchers to indicate the quantity of inventory being to be given to each vaccinator. Unlike the district and provincial offices, the data in tehsil offices is recorded manually in registers. ASV NA stated that there are separate registers for recording stock levels, vaccines successfully administered, as well as vaccines provided to individual UCs. This data is then compiled onto an online database by an operator.

At the UC level, individual vaccinators are responsible for maintaining vaccine forecasts for their fixed sites and/or field areas. According to vaccinator TA, on the day prior to visiting an area he looks up data on the children in that area who need to be vaccinated and those who are awaiting second or third doses. Based on the number of children vaccinated on the following day, the data in registers present in the UC office is updated. Vaccinator SA revealed that the paperwork required for this process is excruciating and wastes precious time. Vaccinators are required to keep record of 3 to 4 different sets of books even though this system can easily be replaced by a web application that would make the process smoother.

In contrast, vaccinator AT believed that the current paper-based system did not require any modification as it was more straight forward to use. Since the lists are made by vaccinators themselves, they find it easier to keep track of the data. Moreover, mobile applications are not feasible for vaccinators working in rural areas where internet quality is poor.

In terms of the quality of forecasting, both the UC and tehsil level employees were satisfied but revealed that quantity inadequacy was an occasional concern. Vaccinator SA revealed that in the first few months of COVID, national lockdowns caused the Penta vaccine to be delayed as flights to the country had been restricted. Similarly, very recently there was shortage of the Rota Vaccine in many districts. Because of this many districts were provided with partial volumes of vaccines while others were provided with no Rota vaccines. However, the vaccinator admitted that such stockouts took place because of the failure in procurement of vaccines rather than the failure of the information system.

Vaccinator AT revealed that one concern for UC employees is that vaccine which is due to be disbursed at the start of the month is often distributed 8 to 10 days into the month. The vaccinators have experience of such an event and therefore keep extra vials for each vaccine stored as a precaution. Although, the information system for vaccine forecasting is quite accurate, there are gaps in contingency protocols should the system ever fail. One such gap was highlighted by AK from Acasus who revealed that there is no uniform way for UCs and Tehsils to raise a flag to the district offices in case of a stockout. Instead, each district had its own protocols in place, meaning that the quality of response to such events is not consistent.

Theme 4: End Delivery

According to Dr. GI, community awareness is a major problem in the country. People should come themselves to get their children vaccinated and keep a track of their children's vaccination. To facilitate them, they have been given vaccination cards with dates mentioned of how the child's previous vaccinations and the next ones. However, even then health seeking behavior of the population is not up to the mark and the EPI staff has to struggle a lot to ensure threshold of immunization of children is reached. Defaulter children are too many unfortunately in the country according to him. Further, in mega districts, not only do district's own children come but out of district and out of province children come too – vaccination done for them in tertiary hospitals tends to go over the target and then the district faces shortage of vaccine for children belonging to the district.

In addition to Dr. GI's comments, ASV MG's comments also shed light on the disinterest showed by the population in the vaccination drives. He recounted that when the vaccinator reaches an area and announces from the mosque that the people who need to be vaccinated should show up, the people may not come because of other commitment. If the vaccinator then tries to go door to door to ask, people find it a nuisance. There are more problems in bigger villages, the first being it is difficult to find a center of town which people can easily access making it difficult for people to show up. Further, sometimes the outreach site be a certain family's home that some other family does not get along with. Again, these people would not come for vaccinations. For such a scenario, such people are asked to visit the nearest BHU.

Further, at UC level there is a lack of spaces to administer vaccines to urban population as mentioned by vaccinator AT. He urged the government to provide dedicated vaccination centers where they can administer vaccines because in urban areas if the locals allow them to

use a place for vaccine administration, then the next month it is probably put up for rent and then they cannot use it. This isn't a problem in villages since the people cooperate a lot there. And sometimes, the contact person is not at home in urban localities and then the vaccinators have to change the house again and again, which creates problems for the locals who want to get the vaccines. Vaccinator AT also recalled the following account: "We faced this issue recently when we did the TCV (typhoid conjugate vaccine) campaign for typhoid. We need dedicated stations, especially in urban '*shehri abadi*', because there is already so much rush so that I can't reach out to all the people via an announcement through the mosque. But if we have a dedicated place where our numbers are mentioned clearly, then people can contact or call us and gather there quickly. We cannot postpone our plans to another day in case people do not gather so we just have to wait. It is also a problem for the families and the children who cannot come around easily."

Vaccinators have to go at great lengths to ensure children don't default. As vaccinator AT mentioned, they maintain a record of children who need to be vaccinated the next day and who defaulted previously. They then call those children who did not show up. He mentioned how only around 8 to 10 children a month default which is very low and these are usually the ones who have gone out of town and the vaccinator has been insured that the child will come.

Once the vaccination process starts, there are other issues. As ASV MG highlighted that the vaccinator cannot move the vaccines to another place once the vial has been opened. So, if a vial with ten vaccines is opened and only five get administered, the vaccinator cannot take these remaining vaccines to another village or area. This makes it very important for people to follow their children's vaccination schedules noted on their vaccination cards reduce wastage due to people not showing up.

Further, a lot of protocols are followed as highlighted by vaccinator AT including the issued syringes being put in safety boxes which are then either burned or taken away. He further added: “For complications, we ask the parents to stay there with the kids for 10-20 minutes after the vaccination. We have also given our numbers so that they can reach out to us in case of any problems. And separate guidelines are also provided regarding the side effects of vaccines such as temperature.”

Theme 5: Managerial decisions

This theme comprised of budgeting, planning and human resources as explored in detail ahead.

Budget

We found useful information from 6 individuals concerning the budget. With the insights gained in our interview process we realized that budgetary issues create two main effects: on vaccine delivery vehicles and on delivery allowances needed by the personnel. There is an additional effect on cold chain equipment maintenance which will also be explored here. Our findings of course attempted to understand this issue better. There are issues related to scarcity of funds itself but that will be explored a bit more below. Other reasons include things like limitations in funds being transferred to cold chain personnel at the district level, bureaucratic red tape, and dependence on donors.

AK from Acasus provided much insights into the two main issues. Firstly, he informed us on the full degree of the issue of allowances. He clarified that it is not an issue of unavailability of funds, but rather it is an issue of transferring them to the right people. The expanded program on immunization has grown from a vertical program to a regularized one. A brief by the World Health Organization describes vertical programs as programs which allow for a rapid addressing of a given health problem through single purpose machinery (Atun et al., 2008). Thus, we can see how regularizing this program represents a fundamental change in the approach the country and province takes towards vaccination. AK highlighted that as a result of this the program has an annual budget with special provisions made for POL. POL (Petrol/Oil/Lubricants) is the term that refers to travel allowances (Masud & Navaratne, 2012).

This could not be done previously because most programs require the extensive Planning Commission Forms 1 and 4 to approved funds. Now the EPI transfers funds to districts and then it is the districts' responsibility to make sure that vaccinators receive their salaries and POL funds. Even so, AK informed us on how there was a large number of vaccinators who had not received their POLs recently. This was because even though the EPI had been allocated funds, they had not able to secure these funds from the finance department of the state. This issue, AK informed us, was later resolved.

The relationship between funds and vaccinators is further complicated by additional government schemes. AK talked at length of one such program called the Enhanced Outreach Activities or EOA. We made additional research to figure out that this program was made to provide funds to bolster immunization coverage (Expanded Program on Immunization, 2020). AK told us that this program began in December 2019 and ended fairly recently covering 136 districts in Punjab. This signifies that this program would have significant impact on the healthcare system at large. The effect of this program was that it provided funds in addition to those that were allocated on the basis of POL provisions. However, the program was discontinued because there were no longer funds for it. Thus, vaccinators were now in a state where they used to receive more funds to do the same work and now, they were receiving less. This created a disincentive to work. AK claimed that such temporary programs are created but lack an effective exit strategy to mitigate such risks to the vaccinators involved.

Next it is important to understand the issue of budgeting for vehicles. Here too AK provides much insight. He informed us that many of the actors involved in the management are in agreement that it is a huge issue that vaccinators lack transportation vehicles. The issue in budgeting for these is the source of funds. Even though the EPI receives a lot of funds, AK

told us that it is difficult to convince the organizations' donors to provide funds earmarked for this purpose. In the future the management wishes to ask organizations like GAVI and the World Bank to provide the funds needed for vehicles.

Lastly, we also talked to an Assistant Director in the EPI, AN. His insights were useful in understanding how budgets worked with regards to paying for repairs. He informed us that there is a procedure to bring up the issues that may come up with the cold chain equipment like ILRs. The first point of contact is always the vendors who provided the fridges like Haier or B Medical. If they are not helpful, the complaint can be taken to the federal EPI too which then tries to expedite the process by talking to vendors as well as other supportive bodies like UNICEF. Of interest to us were AN's comments about the nature of the budgets. We were informed that after the 18th amendment to the Pakistani constitution, there is a larger role for the provinces to do their own budgeting. The federal EPI in this regard plays more of a supportive role.

We can see that issues arise from a reliance on the hierarchies involved in the system to transfer funds, these can be seen between the finance ministry and the EPI as well as between districts and their vaccinators. This is laced with bureaucratic red tape, as AK described it, which slows down the process with its inefficiencies. In addition, we found out that there is a clear lack of foresight involved in creating programs such that they do not affect vaccination activities negatively. While funds inefficiency is not an issue with salaries, finding funds earmarked for buying vehicles does seem to be an issue.

While the findings above talk about budgetary issues, there seem to be contradictions in different views presented. While the Deputy District Health Office Dr. KF decried that they do

not get any allowances for the vaccines, we had the CEO of District Health Office saying that they do not face any budgetary issues of such sort and in fact the system is working very smoothly. One Assistant Superintendent however seemed to find things consistent with what AN mentioned above. He mentioned that his tehsil receives no funds for maintenance of their ILRs which is what AN seems to talk about too when he explained the policy to fix any issues with the fridges. This however may itself be a problem.

Planning

Dr. AS highlighted how there are 2 major junctions in the cold chain where planning is particularly important. The first is when the vaccine enters the country. The vaccines must stay at the ports or other entry point for a certain period of time before the EPI enters them into the country's main cold chain. Since vaccines can sustain sitting idle for a given period of time it is important to manage these times and make sure the vaccines enter temperature-controlled environments soon.

The second junction for Dr. AS was when the vaccines are being distributed. Dr. AS had experienced the program delivering the vaccines itself as its own vertical program. However, we learnt from AK that the nature of the EPI has recently changed. Dr. AS however is still correct to show how the EPI must operate in unison with the provinces especially after the 18th amendment.

To address Dr. AS's second concern about allocations, we can gain insight from Dr. GI who talks about this. He informed us how the province makes set targets in the populations that it feels are important. These include people like infants as well as others like pregnant women. There is the Vaccine Logistics Management Software that has been promulgated to aid

these functions. The system forecasts demand for these segments and in addition also measures consumptions and stocks in different districts. The system however needs the dedication of its staff especially at district and sub-district levels to deliver appropriate amounts of vaccine.

Planning at the top also seems to face issues in harmonizing the cold chain alongside programs made to bolster it as well as contingency plans which are prone to come about. AK from Acasus provides insights from 2 cases. The first one is the case of the enhanced outreach activities which aimed to bolster cold chain coverage and immunization activities by providing some funds to vaccinators. However, this program failed to come up with an effective exit strategy such that it now has created a disincentive of work for cold chain personnel since the program's provided funds are no longer available now. The second case is that of contingencies and with COVID-19. AK informed us on how the government managed the first few batches from Sinopharm and Cansino on its own. This was much to the chagrin of the provinces because the government kept calling them to the capital to pick up more doses while failing to adjust the additional trip and handling expenses into the provincial budgets. Since logistic support still falls on the EPI however it means that the EPI faces a crunch on its own resources too especially its staff to handle these additional activities alongside its regular immunization activities. Thus, spreading cold chain resources thin and less effective.

The role of foreign organizations is also important with regard to planning in the future. AK informed us on how currently GAVI provides much of the vaccines to Pakistan in many different categories. UNICEF in addition is providing funds to bolster Pakistan's cold chain resources. The long-term plan is to be able to procure and handle vaccines more independently. On a lower level, these organizations play a monitoring and evaluating role too.

Union Council vaccinator TA, for example, talked of good experiences with courteous UNICEF officials guiding him on any errors he had made.

With regards to planning it is also important to look at how support is provided to the lower levels where it becomes much more important. This is perhaps true for issues like travel allowances and vehicles which have been addressed elsewhere in this report. Additionally, there is the issue with regards to repairing ILRs. The vaccinators we talked to made complaints that often paying for these has to be borne by themselves. Requests to fix these falls on deaf ears. AN from the federal EPI acknowledged that there exists a system to fix this but following it seems to be dependent on the circumstances of each case. He additionally also told us that they do provide funds for backup power at the district level however it is important to look into funding in some locations where funds are scarcer. Dr. KF informed us of his strategies to fix the ILRs when they are faulty which involve shifting the vaccines in cold boxes to somewhere else while they pay an electrician to fix the ILR. This is also seen with regards to electricity bills at time where there is no planned system to take care of billing costs at lower levels because often the lowest levels do not have official buildings to claim bills against. An interesting caveat here perhaps is how sometimes vaccinators may hold themselves back in asking for too much from their superintendents because of their seniority and in order to show respect to them. Thus, there is an element of self-reliance at these levels.

With regards to management and planning, it is important to voice a sentiment raised particularly by Assistant Superintendent AR. This is in regards to the demarcation of Union Councils. The issue is that some are very large and some are very small. The divisions themselves are often based on political grounds. A better way to demarcate would be on the basis of population so that each vaccinator for areas of 15000 to 20000 people. We were

informed that there are discussions among the policymakers to incorporate this, but it is yet to be seen as a change on the ground.

Lastly, perhaps we can also speak of the feedback process. Dr. KF claimed that they hold monthly feedback meetings with vaccinators while also having WhatsApp groups for communication concerns. It is interesting however to note that vaccinators like TA reported to us how their cellphone allowances have also been slashed recently. Thus, limiting the management's feedback system.

Human Resources

To understand problems related to Human Resources we will first look at the hiring process and then the work involved as part of the cold chain itself.

Dr. KF commented on the cold chain hierarchy and informed us that there was no special staff hired at the Basic Health Unit and Rural Health Center level. However, vaccinators operating around these levels were hired and trained. The federal EPI itself may hire people in the cold chain though. Keeping in mind our research, we were informed that cold chain trainings were given to main store officers who were grade 17 officers of the government. It was this officer's responsibility to then maintain the cold chain. Some may be promoted to trainers too who actually conducted the vaccinators' training.

Speaking of the hiring process, there have been many changes to the process of becoming a vaccinator in the cold chain. ASV MG commented on how there used to simply be a test to clear to become now. But now there is a mandatory year long course too. Besides this the qualifications have also risen to at least FSc. Level education. Of course, this has also meant that their status in terms of government scales has risen from level 5 to level 8.

MG's comments are consistent with ASV AR too. He informs us that there is a requirement for a 2-year diploma. Interestingly he notes how these changes have been fairly recent in having only come to the forefront of things in the last 4-5 years. Though these may be recent trends, we can draw insights from the experience of SA who is currently working as a vaccinator and had taken the course mentioned by MG. SA talks about how the course partially included learning from a book but mostly required fieldwork. The vaccinators had to understand how vaccine transportation and storage worked before being eligible to take an exam with the Punjab Medical Facility. It was only then that they were offered jobs.

It should be noted though that people like AR believe that this is not enough and there should be some course offered after 1 or 2 years to refresh the vaccinators' knowledge and expertise. Such a course does not exist right now. We can however observe that this is partially inconsistent with the ADHO Dr. KF's insistence that vaccinators are quite well trained and knowledgeable. This training is particularly effective, he said, when dealing with foreign vaccines with Vaccine Vial Monitors.

Despite these trainings however there seems to be an issue of understaffing among these employees. Dr. KF acknowledged that understaffing existed outside of his own district. However, within it he spoke about how there were plans to make all contract-based employees permanent because of a project that will run till June 2021.

ASV MG lower down the cold chain provided more insights into why the understaffing issue exists. He outlined 2 reasons. Firstly, coming to secluded areas to work is not attractive to many. Secondly, even after passing the exams for the jobs there are government policies that must be abided by in order to hire and allocate people. ASV AR provided 2 additional reasons.

Firstly, he believed that the job is very tense too which dissuades people from applying. Secondly, he outlines how vaccinators must report to so many people including medical officers, nutrition officers, as well as the district health offices. This made an effect on their self-respect on having so little control and being controlled so much in turn. Thus, few people would opt for this.

Our conversation with Vaccinator AT also showed how this self-respect was also hurt in interactions with officials from the UNICEF. He related an incident on how it was raining one time when he had to go through a surprise evaluation. He had to bring in multiple documents which was difficult to do in the rain. The result was that he was evaluated negatively.

Interestingly, Dr. AS also believes that the EPI operating in parallel with the provinces mean that people have to report on at least 2 levels (federal and provincial). Apart from introducing inefficiencies in the cold chain, it vindicates the sentiments at the tehsil and UC level.

Moving on to the main job, we find that there are several causes for concern. First, we look at career trajectory and salaries. ASV MG informed us that when he joined the department it was new and so promotions did happen frequently. However, he said that now things have changed and in fact there are people who have kept the same job for 25 years. He believed he himself was merely fortunate to have an opportunity to jump to a Tehsil level position. Additionally, MG also believed that they were severely underpaid which will be explored more below. Vaccinator TA vindicated this and informed us on how he has had the same salary for 10 years now.

To further explore these ideas AN and Dr. KF's views are useful. They claimed that career progression is as per government scales. Moving from one grade to the next also meant your salary rose. Dr. KF claimed that they frequently had programs like those related to the polio vaccine with incentives. Additionally, they may earn even more if they put up good performances.

Compensation however cannot be looked at in isolation. A large number of our interviewees had either experienced the plight of having no allowances or had to acknowledge that the issue existed. ASV MG explained this. He said that the government does not provide money for maintenance and fuel for transportation vehicles. This means that the money for these must be borne by the vaccinators themselves.

Vaccinator TA provided more details to this end. In his own case he had been allocated 15 liters per month for his travels. However, the issue was twofold: he needed 25 liters at least and he had not even been reimbursed for the 15 liters allocated. Thus, TA had to resort to covering these expenses on his own. This was the same case with motorcycles provided by WHO which TA had to maintain himself. In Vaccinator AT's case, he claimed to have to spend 8000 rupees of his 28000 rupees salary on petrol for his work. Attempts to be reimbursed of these amounts receive no response. ASV Azmat also claimed that his team had to cover expenses for ILR maintenance on its own.

When asked about the cause of not being provided travel expenses, AT hinted at possible corruption. Though this a major allegation and he did not provide any substantive proof for this. However, he commented on how this makes the job more stressful.

When we asked AN at the federal level about these issues, we were informed that travel expenses are provided but it is up to the provinces themselves on how to facilitate their vaccinators. When further probed on why this was such a recurring issue, he admitted that there are so many vaccinators that it is not possible to facilitate everyone. However, he did defend the immunization program by saying that it tries to facilitate its vaccinators and its partners such as WHO and UNICEF also play a role in paying vaccinators for their travel expenses.

However, it is not just low salaries and slow promotions that are the issue. TA argued that they also are overworked. This perhaps is related to the issue of understaffing highlighted above. AK from Acasus explained how this issue is more pronounced currently (March 2021). This is because the entire responsibility of COVID-19 vaccinations has been given to the EPI along with its usual functions for routine immunization. The result is that the staff face issues in juggling both.

When talking about feedback, we found out that complaints like the requests for funds to repair ILRS fell on deaf ears. Interestingly, Dr. KF at the district level claimed that there is no logistical lacking in the system. He claimed that they received everything requested from the EPI. This is at odds with sentiments shared by those lower down the cold chain.

Thus, here again we find that the profession of vaccinators is not attractive. This alongside government policy leads to issues of understaffing. The vaccinators who are employed face issues concerning lowness of salaries and allowances alongside a degree of acknowledgement of the importance of their position. There is some issue in increasing salaries

but there is also the issue of managing provided allowance funds because it was not clear where the allocations were being spent.

CHAPTER 5. DISCUSSION, RECOMMENDATIONS, AND CONCLUSION

Discussion and Recommendations

In the context of transport, there was a visible agreement at all levels of the cold chain that there was rarely any damage to vaccines during transit. Most employees at any level could not recall instances of vaccines being damaged due to a mishap in transport. At each level of transportation, there were adequate contingencies in place to handle vehicle malfunctions. However, federal employees did reveal that in recent months, EPI had to allocate a significant number of vehicles to the transport of COVID vaccines. Owing to this, vehicles with ILRs installed in them are currently being utilized to a much greater extent than previously anticipated. This over utilization might result in more frequent malfunctions in the future. Up until now, these vehicles have been highly reliable owing to which many of the contingency protocols in place for their malfunction remain untested as well. One possible solution to this issue is the procurement of new vehicles which would reduce the extent to which a vehicle is utilized. Another solution is to reduce the total volume of vaccines being transported from federal stores to provincial warehouses. This can be done by allowing districts in and around the federal capital the ability to procure their vaccines directly from the federal store. This would not only put a stop to the wastage of resources and time, it will also avoid occasional vaccine stock outs on tehsil level.

Further, currently the district management plays no role in ensuring the vaccine reaches the UC level from the tehsil level safely. Further, the process of getting the vaccine from the tehsil level is not very efficient as mentioned by vaccinator AT and it may take an entire day just to get the vaccines. Tehsil administration can coordinate with their vaccinators to reduce wait times so the vaccinators are present in the BHU for longer so in case someone visits for vaccination, they

do not have to leave without it. The ideal situation as pointed out by many interviewees would be to have a vehicle, perhaps a minivan as requested by ASV AR and AZ, which would transport the vaccine from the tehsil level to all the BHUs. The administration should focus on making this happen in the long run at least to increase efficiency of transport in the cold chain.

Unlike transport damage, failures in warehousing are a very prominent source of vaccine damage. The most interesting point here is that there is a stark difference in the quality of resources available to federal warehouses as compared to warehouses down the cold chain. Whilst all levels of the cold chain are equipped with ILRs (or cold rooms in case of federal and provincial stores), UC and Tehsil level ILRs lack in quality, quantity and can often malfunction. In response to such malfunctions, the repair and maintenance process is long, requires equipment to be shipped back to district offices, and in some cases requires UC and Tehsil level employees to bear the expenses. The entire process would be much more reliable if there were to be a designated team in each district, who could simply travel to warehouses and health centers with faulty equipment. The logistics of managing such a team would be far cheaper than the current system. Moreover, it would help save time as minor malfunctions could be resolved within the 10–12-hour vaccine maintaining window of the ILR. This would also help protect vaccine packaging as there would not be any need to transfer vaccines into freezers. Lastly, it would make the billing process more straight forward for the district if their own employees handled the repairs.

Power outages are also a common concern at both UC and Tehsil level. Warehouses and centers at these levels do not have backup generators while some are also not having a UPS. In truth, the contingencies for warehouse malfunctions are more effective than the actual protocols as they are the main reason vaccines are not being damaged. However, such effective

contingencies cloak the fact that there is a substantial lack of investment for vaccine storage at the lower levels of the cold chain. The fact that employees are forced to transfer vaccines from ILRs to their homes to maintain the cold chain shows the gravity of these issues. Further, the already limited ILRs are few and sometimes malfunctioning. Some solutions to these problems include increasing the number of solar powered ILRs, especially in UCs without any UPS backups. There should be an extra generator in each district that can be transported to tehsils and UCs in case of longer/unexpected power outages. Promisingly, there are investments being made as there are additions of 3000 ILRs, 89 cold rooms and freezer rooms, 6500 vaccine carriers and cold boxes to further strengthen our cold chain as stated by Mr. NA.

Quantity inadequacy is a direct consequence of unreliable forecasting mechanism. However, the current forecasting system does seem to be quite reliable as the only cases of stockouts reported are due to issues in procurement as a result of COVID rather than forecasting and disbursements. At the same time, there is further room for improvement so that potential future issues in forecasting can be identified and mitigated. One manner of doing this is by targeting the current causes of inefficiencies. For this reason, there should be an effort to develop a uniform protocol towards vaccine stockouts at UC, Tehsil, and District level. For this reason, there should be a committee which handles such stockouts for each type of vaccine. Depending on the type of vaccine required, warehouses should be able to contact the committee and sort everything out. Moreover, the VLMIS system should be updated so that it automatically raises a flag to relevant departments whenever there is likelihood of a stockout.

When talking about budgets, we have already learnt that there are issues with allocating allowances to vaccinators and earmarking funds for travel vehicles. Additionally, there are also concerns with an insistence on solving problems thought to be linked with budgets instead with

procedures like seeking help from vendors and then the federal EPI for ILRs. There is of course also the issue of managing budgets in unison with the provinces. The reliance on agencies like GAVI is quite important here as earlier noted by Brenzel, Sanderson, Galayda, Masud, and Haq too. These organizations are an inescapable fact and, thus, it is important for policy collaborations with these donor agencies to reframe the issue of low cold chain reliability as one of resource deficiencies at the UC and Tehsil levels. Furthermore, as highlighted in our findings, there is a need to expedite the devolution process of power. This would mean that people in the federal EPI would be less burdened in making sure that budgets are being sent out. Furthermore, a locus of power closer to people making requests for imbursements is likely to reduce bureaucratic muddle and thereby make it more likely to address these concerns especially since money is not the main problem here.

From our findings on planning, we can note how software and particularly the logistics management system is immensely important to it. Riaz et al have found that vaccine coverage is equally important as vaccine effectiveness in a public health system. Dr. GI's awareness of this system's uses must extend lower down the cold chain too. Additionally, the public health department must learn that its cold chain systems have been ill-suited to face not only contingencies but also the effects of other health programs. The fortunate thing about this is that the issue can be simply corrected by, firstly, putting in efforts to mitigate future strains on the system by identifying the limitations of the cold chain that were exposed by COVID-19 especially with regards to the institutions of EPI alongside the low staff numbers employed in maintaining the cold chain and then deploying the plan when such an issue arises again; secondly, there must be no future public health programs promulgated without a proper exit strategy and a proper risk analysis. Moreover, the cold chain has failed to properly implement its policies with issues

like vaccine allowances and union council vaccine billings. This has been addressed before with regards to the need to expedite the process of devolution started by the 18th amendment. The mismatch between cold chain personnel to populations also needs to be addressed. The measure proposed in our findings must be implemented here: dividing vaccinators on the basis of population rather than union council demarcations. This would sidestep political influences that go into demarcating union council boundaries as well as making a more equitable distribution of personnel. This would be also likely to be accepted since it has been suggested by the personnel themselves.

With Human Resources, it is also important to restate the main issues. The issue of understaffing is related to how the job has become unattractive. There is an opportunity to address the concern of career progression by enabling greater ownership among personnel during a process of devolution of power which is likely to require people who are experienced about the workings of the cold chain. The provincial and federal governments should collaborate to make urgent efforts to train more vaccinators since the COVID vaccination is also administered by the same limited number of vaccinators. There is already a shortage and COVID vaccination will add more strain to the limited work force. Coupled with this, the district management should undertake efforts to reduce procedural delays and hire vaccinators quickly once they pass the exams. This is very important since the entire UC relies on the vaccinator's presence – if no vaccinator is present the number of children defaulting would grow inevitably. The district management also needs to ensure the vaccinators are paid for their fuel expenses because it significantly decreases morale of the vaccinators when they have to pay for the fuel themselves given their already lowly salaries. There needs to be a contingency plan incorporated

by the district management because currently the absence of one vaccinator delays all vaccination plans.

Lastly, there is still a lack of motivation in the public regarding getting vaccinations on time. The government needs to continue undertaking awareness programs as well as dedicate areas as vaccination centers especially in urban areas where vaccinators struggle a lot to reduce the number of default children. A more intense action to urge people to get vaccinated could be inspired from what the KPI's provincial government did when they released arrest warrants to 1200 parents and guardians for refusal to take part in the polio vaccination program. The government can also mobilise religious leaders to tackle social resistance (Shakeel et al., 2019).

Conclusion

Given the extensive explanation and discussions of our findings from our interviews, it is possible to develop an opinion on the degree of reliability of the cold chain under question. Although there seems to be a reliable force to the cold chain at higher levels such as the federal, this version of the cold chain changes drastically if we go to the Tehsil and Union Council levels. Despite the claims of some officials, there are many issues in the cold chain system that need to be addressed here. With deliveries there is the constant issue with how certain protocols such as those related to emergencies are not tested. Not only are current routes often inefficient they seem quite illogical at times. There is a huge gap in involving the districts in particular with vaccine delivery too. The COVID-19 pandemic has, furthermore, exposed a complacency in the system. The faulty ILRs must now be shared with COVID-19 pressures, the already overburdened vaccinators and ASVs must take on more work, and reliance on buffer stocks may rise. The need for vehicles will also be felt.

Though we have seen that the system is reliable against some faults that happen during transportation, we must also note that warehousing practices do not make the cold chain reliable. This can be especially seen with an overreliance on the ingenuity of its vaccinators and other staff at these levels which in fact act as crutches to make the system reliable. This can be seen with one contrast: while the VLMIS provides opportunity to cater to quantity availabilities better, there is a risk of many children defaulting due to the simple limitations of not having reliable vaccine centers or, perhaps more important, dedicated vaccinators.

The cold chain system relies a lot on its vaccinators to pay for vaccine transportations and sometimes even upkeeping ILRs. Not only are they overworked with no contingency plans

in case they fail, but they are also not reimbursed for their travels raising questions on the reliability of a system that is so dependent on such people.

Issues in planning at large can also be seen by how the EPI is overburdened managing its own activities, coordinating with provinces, and managing logistics for the COVID-19 vaccines. In addition, the program is often a victim of the government's own public health programs which affect its cold chain staff.

Our recommendations begin with a need to invest in transportation vehicles as well as ILRs at the lowest levels of the cold chains. There is also a need to create accountability measures to counter the aloof management at higher levels through things like an online portal. Additional dedicated staff is also needed to address issues like transportation and addressing or stopping faults in the ILRs. The VLMIS system, moreover, needs to be updated and returned to favor with policymakers since its efficient usage can raise the alarm on potential stockouts. It is also important for the cold chain to advocate for the devolution of power which can potentially empower the Union Councils and remove much problems that arise from bureaucratic muddle and a lack of attention given by those higher up. Partnerships with organizations like GAVI must be reemphasized. Lastly, there is a pressing need to expedite allowance payments as well as the recruitment process. Perhaps it is most important that the conditions of the vaccinators improve if the cold chain is to be made reliable.

Though there is potential for more research with regards to exploring the effectiveness of some of our suggestion and perhaps with focusing on particular issues like salary stagnancy, this report has achieved much of what it set out to do: making a judgement on the cold chain

system in Punjab, understanding the issues faced by its stakeholders, and providing some recommendations to address those issues

APPENDIX A: INTERVIEW GUIDE

Metric	Questions
Delivery delay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What do you have to say about the problem of delivery delays? - How big of a problem is delivery delays?
a. Inventory shortage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What do you think about the problem of inventory shortage?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Replenishment delay 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How big of a problem do you think are delays between orders for the vaccine?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient warehouse space 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is your take on the availability of warehouse space?
b. Unreasonable vehicle scheduling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is your take on vehicle scheduling issues?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequate transport vehicle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What do you think about the transport vehicles in the system?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequate delivery staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What about the staff involved in delivery?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improper route planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the major routes you use for vaccine delivery?
c. Emergencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What kind of emergencies lead to delivery delays? - Which emergency is the most significant?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bad weather 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic accident 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicle breakdown 	
Quantity Inadequacy	
a. Information system error	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How does the department/organization incorporate data collected from its Vaccine Logistics Management Information System? - What is its coverage like?

Unqualified products	
a. Packaging processing damage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the packaging quality like? - What can you tell us about the extent of packaging damage?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor packaging material 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the possible packaging defects that can lead to damage?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improper loading and unloading 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the risks of damage during loading/unloading?
b. Warehousing damage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What mechanisms are in place to sustain vaccine quality in warehouses?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cold storage cooling equipment failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the status of storage equipment? - To what extent can equipment failure damage vaccines? - How often does it occur?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cold storage monitoring system failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What systems are in place to detect accidents/equipment failures? - How reliable are these systems?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cold store power failure and cold storage standby power failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the status of power supply and standby power sources? - How prevalent is power failure at this level of the cold chain? - How does the cold chain cope with such events?
c. Transport damage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are cold chain systems maintained during transport? - What are the common sources of system failure in transport?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improper driver operation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How crucial is the role of the driver in preventing vaccine damages during transit?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicle cooling system failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the status of vehicle cooling system for transit? - Do these systems sustain during delays or extreme weather conditions?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicle monitoring system failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the status of vehicle monitoring system during transit? - Are there actions that can be taken during transport to avoid damage to vaccines?

APPENDIX B: FAULT TREE

APPENDIX C: FINDINGS TREE

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